

AACR ON CAMPUS MALAYSIA 2025

*Bridging the translational gap between
pre-clinical, clinical and implementation studies.*

CATEGORY: PREVENTION AND EARLY DETECTION

ABSTRACT # CC9

Development of CARE CRC Tool for Ideal Surveillance and Early Detection of Relapse Among Individuals with Colorectal Cancer in Sabah

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Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the second leading cause of cancer mortality in Malaysia, with relapse representing a major driver of poor long-term survival. In Sabah, geographical barriers, fragmented oncology services, and limited surveillance capacity exacerbate these outcomes. This study aimed to develop, validate, and translate a relapse prediction model tailored to the Sabah population into a web-based clinical decision support tool, the CARE CRC Tool. A retrospective cohort of 500 patients with histologically confirmed CRC diagnosed between 2015 and 2020 was analyzed, comprising 250 relapse and 250 non-relapse cases. 10 routinely available clinicopathological and treatment variables were examined. Multivariable logistic regression identified six significant predictors ($p < 0.05$) of relapse; Stage (III–IV), lymphovascular invasion, perineural invasion, carcinoembryonic level, incomplete chemotherapy, and tumor grade. The model demonstrated strong discrimination (AUC 0.85), good calibration, and maintained performance on temporal validation (AUC 0.83). The model was integrated into the CARE CRC Tool, enabling automated risk stratification and standardized clinical recommendations. Pilot testing with oncology clinicians confirmed excellent means in usability (4.6 ± 0.5), comprehensibility (4.5 ± 0.6), perceived clinical utility (4.7 ± 0.4) and overall satisfaction (4.4 ± 0.6). The study demonstrates that predictive analytics can be effectively contextualized for resource-limited settings, supporting risk-stratified surveillance, more efficient allocation of oncology resources, and improved equity in follow-up care.

DEVELOPMENT OF CARE CRC TOOL FOR IDEAL SURVEILLANCE AND EARLY DETECTION OF RELAPSE AMONG INDIVIDUALS WITH COLORECTAL CANCER IN SABAH

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INTRODUCTION

- Colorectal cancer (CRC) is **Malaysia's second leading cause of cancer death**
- In Sabah, relapse worsens survival due to **late diagnosis, limited oncology services, and poor surveillance**
- Only two referral centers (QEH and SWACH)** manage CRC cases, leaving rural patients at risk
- Most survivors receive uniform follow-up intervals** despite vast geographic and financial barriers, **causing missed appointments and delayed detection**
- Current surveillance treats all patients equally but CARE-CRC helps clinicians see who needs care first**

OBJECTIVE

To develop, validate, and translate a relapse prediction model into a web-based clinical decision support tool (CARE-CRC Tool) for Sabah

RESULTS

Predictors : 6 Significant predictors

Predictor	β Coefficient	Adjusted Odds Ratio	95% CI	p-value
Stage (III-IV vs I-II)	1.19	3.28	2.05-5.26	<0.001
Lymphovascular invasion	1.01	2.74	1.79-4.19	<0.001
Perineural invasion (PNI)	0.88	2.41	1.58-3.68	<0.001
CEA ≥ 5 ng/ml	0.52	1.68	1.12-2.53	0.012
Incomplete chemotherapy	0.67	1.95	1.29-2.94	0.002
Surgical margin (Positive)	0.35	1.42	0.76-2.65	0.264
Postoperative complication	0.33	1.39	0.84-2.29	0.204
ASA score ≥3	0.25	1.28	0.85-1.94	0.239
Family history present	0.32	1.37	0.83-2.25	0.215
Tumour grade	0.18	1.2	0.70-2.05	0.003

Model Performance (ROC) : AUC 0.83 (Strong discrimination)

Calibration : Good agreement between predicted and observed risk

Domain	Mean Score (1-5)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Usability	4.6	0.5
Comprehensibility	4.5	0.6
Perceived Clinical Utility	4.7	0.4
Overall Satisfaction	4.4	0.6

Clinician Satisfaction : Excellent in usability (4.6±0.5) and perceived clinical utility (4.7±0.4)

Total Score Range	Risk Category	Predicted Relapse Probability	Interpretation
0-6	Low Risk	< 10%	Patient have minimal likelihood of relapse
7-14	Moderate Risk	10-35%	Patients have intermediate relapse risk
15 - 25	High Risk	> 35%	Patients have substantial likelihood of relapse

METHODOLOGY

Study Design : Retrospective cohort (2015-2020)

Setting & Timeline: Queen Elizabeth (QEH) and Sabah Women & Children Hospital (SWACH). Data from 2015-2018 for model development, and 2019-2020 for temporal validation

Sample (N) : 500 CRC patients using where 250 relapse, and 250 non-relapse using a **purposive balanced** sampling

4 Phases

1 Model Development : **10 Clinicopathological Predictors** Selected

2 Model Validation : Internal and External assessing for **discrimination & calibration**

3 Integration into CARE CRC : (Web-based application) where **predictors' scores are calculated automatically** and **risks of relapse** are generated

4 Pilot evaluation - 20 Clinicians evaluated using **5-point likert scale**

Analysis is using SPSS Version 26

DISCUSSION

- First locally validated relapse predictor tool in Sabah and Malaysia**
- Practical, interpretable, and clinician-friendly
- Automates risk stratification**, improves efficiency, and supports equitable follow-up.
- Scalable model**

IMPACT FACTOR: Supports Malaysia's National Cancer Control Plan, Digital Health Blueprints & aligns with National Health White Paper

FUTURE ROADMAPS
UMS → MOH Clinics/hospitals → MySejahtera Integration → NGOs/Private

CONCLUSION

- CARE-CRC Tool is a validated, user-friendly digital solution that **strengthens relapse surveillance in Sabah**.
- Saves oncology resources, helps clinicians prioritize who needs the care first** and bridges rural-urban disparities

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